

Non-linear Assessment of Gait Impairments of Patients with Parkinson's Disease using Entropy, Complexity, and Poincaré Section-based Features.

P. A. Pérez-Toro · J. C. Vásquez-Correa · T. Arias-Vergara · J. R. Orozco-Aroyave · E. Nöth

Received: date / Accepted: date

Abstract Parkinson's Disease is a progressive disorder of the nervous system that affects the motor system of the patients, producing several impairments in muscles and limbs. One of the major manifestations of the disease appears in gait, and typically causes disability of the patients. Gait assessment appears as an useful tool to support the diagnosis process and to evaluate the neurological state of the patients. The gait of the patients is mainly evaluated from signals captured with inertial sensors attached to the limbs of the patients, where kinematics features are commonly computed. On the other hand, there are non-linear effects of the gait process that cannot be properly characterized with the kinematic features. This study proposes the use several non-linear dynamics features to assess the gait impairments of Parkinson's patients. We consider classical non-linear features such as the correlation dimension, the largest Lyapunov exponent, and the Hurst exponent, among others. In addition we propose a novel non-linear analysis based on applying a Gaussian mixture model to find clusters in Poincaré sections. The non-linear dynamics features are used to discriminate between Parkinson's patients and healthy subjects, and

to classify patients in several stages of the disease. The results indicate that it is possible to discriminate between patients and healthy subjects with accuracies up to 88% and to classify patients in several stages of the disease with accuracies up to 65%. As far as we know, this is one of the first studies that considers a full non-linear dynamics analysis to assess the gait impairments of patients with Parkinson's disease.

Keywords Parkinson's Disease · Non-linear Dynamics · Poincare Section · Gait assessment · Classification · Prediction · Inertial Sensors

1 Introduction

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a neuro-degenerative disorder characterized by the progressive loss of dopaminergic neurons in the mid brain [1]. The motor symptoms include lack of coordination, tremor, rigidity and postural instability. Gait impairments appear in most of patients and include freezing, shuffling, and festinating gait. The standard scale to evaluate the neurological state of the patients is the Movement Disorder Society-Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS) [2]. The third section of the scale contains 14 items to evaluate the deficits in the lower limbs of the patients. The therapy mainly focuses on treating the symptoms of the patients with individual medication. This medication always has to be adjusted according to the current stage of disease.

Gait changes are a hallmark of PD, where the main symptoms include reductions in speed, decreased step length, altered cadence, and increased gait variability. While gait abnormalities are not pronounced in the early stages, their prevalence and severity increases with

P. A. Pérez-Toro, J. C. Vásquez-Correa, T. Arias-Vergara, and J. R. Orozco-Aroyave are with Faculty of Engineering, University of Antioquia UdeA, Medellín, Colombia.

J. C. Vásquez-Correa, T. Arias-Vergara, J. R. Orozco-Aroyave, and E. Nöth are with Pattern Recognition Lab, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany.

T. Arias-Vergara is with Ludwig-Maximilians-University, Munich, Germany.

*Corresponding author: jcamilo.vasquez@udea.edu.co

the disease progression [3]. More than 85% of PD patients develop gait impairments after three years of diagnosis [3]. The potential consequences of gait impairments in PD may include increased disability, increased risk of falls, and reduced quality of life. As the disease progresses, PD patients typically exhibit shuffling gait with a forward-stooped posture and festinating gait. These characteristics make the patient to spend a lot of energy, which causes that the walking routine leads the patients to their maximum metabolic capacity [4]. Gait impairments also include the presence of bradykinesia, rigidity, and postural instability. In addition, PD patients consider mobility and walking limitations to be one of the most impaired aspects of the disease. Patients consistently identify improvement in walking as the most relevant outcome when rating the success of the treatment for the disease [5].

1.1 State of the art

In related studies, the scientific community has shown a growing interest about the gait analysis to evaluate the neurological state of PD patients. Gait analysis of the patients have been performed commonly with inertial sensors e.g., accelerometers and gyroscopes attached to the shoes of the patients [6, 7, 8].

One of the first studies was performed in [9], where the authors classified gait signals captured from 42 PD patients and 39 healthy control (HC) subjects using the eGait system [10]. The system consisted of accelerometers and gyroscopes attached to the lateral heel of the shoe. The participants performed several exercises, including the straight walking of 10 meters 4 times (4×10), heel-toe tapping, and circling foot movements. The authors computed several spectral and statistical features from the gait signals, including the energy content in several frequency bands, the variance, the root-mean square energy, among others. The classification of HC subjects and PD patients was performed with several classifiers. The results indicated that it was possible to classify PD patients vs. HC subjects with accuracies up to 82%. The accuracy improved up to 91% when considering only PD patients in severe state of the disease. In [7] the authors proposed an algorithm to segment the strides of PD patients based on the dynamic time warping (DTW) algorithm. The authors developed a stride template using gait information from 25 HC subjects. The segmentation algorithm was tested with information from 40 HC subjects, 15 PD patients and 25 geriatric patients, who performed a 40 m straight walking exercise. The proposed approach showed to be accurate to segment the steps of the PD patients (F-score up to

0.9). In [8] the authors considered inertial sensors attached to the chest and to the knees to evaluate the neurological state of 34 PD patients according to the UPDRS score. The participants performed several exercises, including 20 meters walking, rising from a chair, and foot tapping. The authors computed kinematic features such as the standing time, the stride length, the stride velocity, among others. The regression algorithm was based on K-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithm to predict the UPDRS score of the patients. A Spearman's correlation coefficient (ρ) of 0.60 was reported for the prediction. In [11] the authors proposed a statistical transformation called shifted one-dimensional local binary pattern domain to classify gait signals from PD patients and HC subjects captured in different conditions and with a different experimental protocol. The authors considered three different databases for their experiments, forming a dataset with signals captured from 93 PD patients and 73 HC subjects. The data were collected using 8 sensors to measure the pressure of the foot when the subjects walk. The authors computed several statistical features from the available data. The extracted features were transformed with the proposed method, and they were classified using eight different algorithms. The highest accuracy was obtained with a multi-layer perceptron classifier (88.9%). In [12] the authors classified gait signals obtained from 15 PD patients and 16 HC subjects. The signals were captured with ultra-thin force-sensitive switches placed inside the shoes of the participants. The authors computed several kinematics features such as the stride time, the swing time, the stance time, among others. Afterwards, the features extracted from each foot were used to compute a phase synchronization coefficient and the conditional entropy with the aim to analyze the gait rhythm fluctuations between both feet. The authors considered several classifiers. The most accurate results were reported with a multi-layer perceptron, where an area under the receiving operating characteristic curve (AUC) of 0.928 was reported. In previous studies [13] we computed kinematics features from gait signals captured with the eGait system [10] to evaluate the neurological state of the patients. A Spearman's correlation of up to 0.72 was reported between the MDS-UPDRS-III score of the patients and the predicted values obtained with a Support Vector Regressor (SVR). Recently in [14], the authors proposed new features to assess gait impairments of PD patients. Those new features were the peak forward acceleration in the loading phase and peak vertical acceleration around heel-strike, which encode the engagement in stride initiation and the hardness of the impact at heel-strike, respectively. The results indicated that the proposed features correlate with the

disease progression and the loss of postural agility/stability of the patients. In [15] the authors aimed to detect freezing of gait (FoG) episodes in PD patients using a deep learning approach. Data was collected from 21 PD patients with FoG using a waist-placed inertial sensor. The exercises performed by the participants included free walking inside an apartment, walking ten meters outdoors, and rising from a chair. The authors considered a six-layer one-dimensional convolutional neural network (CNN), whose inputs were formed by spectral representations of consecutive time intervals. In total, the input of the CNN consisted of 64 frequency bins obtained from 9 inertial sensors (3-axis accelerometer, gyroscope and magnetometer) along with those obtained from the previous time interval. Accuracies of up to 90% were reported for the addressed problem.

Although most of the studies considered only kinematics, spectral, or statistical features to assess the gait impairments of PD patients, there are some studies that evaluated the non-linear effects of the walking process of PD patients using Non-Linear Dynamics (NLD) features. For instance, in [16], the authors performed a combined analysis of spectral, statistical, kinematics, and NLD features to characterize gait signals of 14 HC subjects, 10 PD patients and 11 patients with peripheral neuropathy. The exercises consisted on 3 minutes of continuous walking on a treadmill. The NLD features included the largest Lyapunov exponent (LLE), the Lempel Ziv complexity (LZC), several entropy measures, among others. The extracted features were compared for the three groups using the Kruskal-Wallis and Mann-Whitney tests. Significant differences were reported in features such as the LZC and the cross-entropy, which allow to discriminate between HC subjects and PD patients. In [17] the authors classified 13 PD patients, 13 Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis patients and 13 Huntington patients and 13 HC subjects using data obtained from force-sensitive resistors [18]. The authors computed NLD features such as the Shannon entropy, the recurrence rate, and recurrence quantification analysis (RQA). The classification was performed with a support Vector Machine (SVM) and a Probabilistic Neural Network to discriminate between patients with the different neuro-degenerative diseases and the HC subjects. The classification followed a leave-one-out cross-validation strategy, which could be slightly optimistic, and report accuracies close to 100%.

1.2 Contribution

This study proposes the use of several NLD features to model the walking process of PD patients and HC subjects. The features include correlation dimension (CD),

LLE, Hurst exponent (HE), LZC, and several entropy measures, which have proved to be accurate for the NLD analysis of PD [16,19,20]. In addition, we propose a new set of NLD features to model the dispersion of Poincaré sections using Gaussian mixture models (GMM), which allow to represent the Poincaré sections as a probability distribution. The extracted features are used to discriminate between PD patients and HC subjects; and to classify PD patients in several stages of the disease. The classification is performed with three different algorithms: KNN, SVM and Random Forest (RF). Additionally, we aim to predict the neurological state of the patient according to the MDS-UPDRS-III score using an SVR. The results of the proposed approach indicates that it is possible to classify PD patients and HC subjects with accuracies up to 86.7%, and to discriminate between PD patients in several stages of the disease with accuracies up to 65.2%. As far as we know, this is one of the first papers that consider only NLD features to characterize the walking process of PD patients.

2 Methods

2.1 Non-linear dynamics and entropy features.

2.1.1 Phase space.

The phase space reconstruction is the first step for the NLD analysis. The Takens’s Theorem [21] is used for such a purpose, and guarantees that for a noise-free time-series exists a dimension m such that the vectors S_t are equivalents to the phase space vectors [22]. For a time series s_t , a phase space can be constructed using Equation 1, where the time-delay τ is computed by the first minimum of the mutual information function, and the embedding dimension m is found using the false neighbors method [23].

$$\mathbf{S}_t = \{s_t, s_{t-\tau}, \dots, s_{t-(m-1)\tau}\} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1 shows the phase space obtained from gait signals corresponding to 20 meters walking with a stop at 10 meters from four subjects: (A) HC subject, (B) PD patient in low stage of the disease, (C) PD patient in intermediate stage of the disease, (D) PD patient in severe stage of the disease. Note that the phase space for the HC subject exhibits well defined trajectories and a clear recurrence. Conversely the trajectories of the phase space for the patients are more dispersed, especially when the neurological state of the patients is severe. Several NLD features can be computed from

Fig. 1 Phase Space from gait signal produced by: A: HC subject, B: PD patient in low state of the disease (MDS-UPDRS subscore for lower limbs =6), C: PD patient in intermediate state of the disease (MDS-UPDRS subscore for lower limbs =13), D: PD patient in severe state of the disease (MDS-UPDRS subscore for lower limbs =34)

the phase space to assess the complexity and stability of the walking process.

2.1.2 Correlation Dimension.

This feature establishes a measure over the exact space that is occupied by an attractor in the multidimensional space where is built [22]. The computation of CD starts with the estimation of the correlation sum is a probability function where the possible cases are the points that are contained in a hyper-sphere of radius ε . This sum is defined for a set of points x_n using Equation 2.

$$C(\varepsilon) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N(N-1)} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=i+1}^N \theta(\varepsilon - |x_i - x_j|) \quad (2)$$

Where θ is the Heaviside step function, $C(\varepsilon)$ counts the distances between x_i and x_j lower than the threshold ε , and N is the number of embedded points. To compute the CD, a linear regression of $\ln(C(\varepsilon))$ vs. $\ln(\varepsilon)$ is performed. The slope of the resultant line for a small ε value corresponds to CD [22].

2.1.3 Approximate entropy

Entropy is an uncertainty measurement, it can characterize the disorder of a system. The Approximate Entropy (ApEn) is based on searching similar patterns into a time-series to provide a general regularity measure. ApEn can be applied on relatively short and noisy data. After computing the correlation sum C_i defined

by Equation 2, we define an average version using Equation 3, where N is the number of points in the embedded time-series. Two parameters, m and r must be chosen before computing this entropy, where m is the pattern length and r is the effective filter. ApEn is defined as the increment of $\phi^m(r)$ between two immediate steps of m , i.e., $\text{ApEn}(m, r, N) = \phi^m(r) - \phi^{m+1}(r)$.

$$\phi^m(r) = \frac{1}{N - m + 1} \sum_{i=1}^{N-m+1} \log C_i^m(r) \quad (3)$$

2.1.4 Sample Entropy

The ApEn estimation may be affected by $\log(0)$ in the time-series. To avoid this occurrence, each template vector counts itself in the comparisons. In addition, the ApEn hardly dependent of the time-series length, making short time series have a lower estimation than the expected, and also affecting the measure consistency. The sample entropy was proposed in [24] as a measure capable of dealing with the problems of ApEn. SampEn is defined according to Equation 4, where m , r and N are defined as for the ApEn, and A is the $\phi^m(r)$ measure without auto-comparisons to avoid the occurrence of $\log(0)$ in the estimation.

$$\text{SampEn}(m, r, N) = -\log \frac{A^m(r)}{A^{m+1}(r)} \quad (4)$$

2.1.5 ApEn and SampEn with Gaussian kernel.

Although the improvement offered by SampEn over ApEn, the validity and accuracy of the estimated regularity is affected by the discontinuity of the Heaviside function. In [25], the authors proposed a solution, which consists of replacing the Heaviside step function with a Gaussian kernel in the estimation of the correlation sum C_i , which is estimated using Equation 5 when the kernel is considered.

$$C_i^m(r) = \frac{1}{N - m} \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^{N-m+1} \exp\left(-\frac{(\|x(i), x(j)\|_1)^2}{10r^2}\right) \quad (5)$$

2.1.6 Largest Lyapunov Exponent

The LLE measures the sensitivity to initial conditions of the signal according to the rate at which the nearby trajectories of the phase space converge or diverge. This feature gives information about the stability properties of the time-series. LLE quantifies the exponential divergence of the neighbor paths in a phase space, i.e.,

it measures the degree of aperiodicity of a given signal. After the reconstruction of the phase-space, the nearest neighbor of each point in the trajectory is located. The nearest neighbor $x_{\hat{j}}$ minimizes the Euclidean distance from the reference point x_j according to Equation 6, where $d_j(0)$ is the initial divergence between x_j and $x_{\hat{j}}$, and $|| ||$ is the Euclidean distance between two points.

$$d_j(0) = \min ||x_j - x_{\hat{j}}|| \quad (6)$$

To guarantee different trajectories between the neighbors paths, the points $x_{\hat{j}}$ and x_j have to be separated a distance larger than the average period of the signal in the time series. The LLE is estimated as the mean separation rate between the nearest neighbors, according to the Oseledec theorem [26], which is expressed according to Equation 7, where λ corresponds to the LLE, $d(t)$ is the mean divergence in an instant t and A is a constant for normalization.

$$d(t) = Ae^{\lambda t} \quad (7)$$

2.1.7 Hurst Exponent

The HE is used to evaluate the long-term dependency of the time-series. HE is a smoothness measurement of a fractal time series, which quantifies the chaotic dynamics of a system. HE is defined by Equation 8, where T is the duration of the sample of data and R/S is the re-scaled range by the standard deviation.

$$T^{\text{HE}} = \frac{R}{S} \quad (8)$$

2.1.8 Recurrence Probability Density Entropy (RPDE).

Another entropy measure considered to analyze chaotic and deterministic dynamic of gait signals is the Recurrence Probability Density Entropy (RPDE), which is computed by the close returns method [27]. Let's assume there is a small circle $B(S_{t_0}, r)$ with radius $r > 0$, which is located close to the data embedded point S_{t_0} . After, the time instant t_1 when the first orbit returns to the sphere is recorded. The difference between two time instants is the recurrence time $T = t_1 - t_0$. The recurrence time is computed for all embedded data points S_t , forming an histogram of recurrence times $R(T)$, which is normalized to give the recurrence probability density according to Equation 9, where T_{max} is the maximum recurrence time.

$$\text{RPDE} = -\frac{R(t) \cdot \ln(R(t))}{\ln(T_{max})} \quad (9)$$

2.1.9 Detrended Fluctuation Analysis (DFA).

The Detrended Fluctuation Analysis (DFA) is a simple method to identify different stages of the same system with different behaviour of the scale. To compute the stochastic component of the gait process, DFA is considered. DFA searches trends over intervals of size L from the signal, which allow to obtain long-term dependencies of the time-series. This is similar to the HE, except that DFA may be applied to time-series whose underlying statistics are non-stationary. In addition, DFA allows to detect the embedded intrinsic self-similarity in a non-stationary time-series and avoids the spurious detection of the apparent self-similarity.

2.1.10 Lempel Ziv complexity

This feature is related to the number of different patterns lies along a sequence. It reflects the order that is retained in a one-dimensional temporal pattern or in a string of n symbols. The algorithm is based on the original string reconstruction through copy operations and symbols insertions in the new string. The time-series $x(t)$ have to be transformed into a symbolic sequence $P = \{s(1), s(2), \dots, s(t)\}$ to compute LZC. Related studies have shown that binary codification is suitable for physiologic time-series [28,29]. To perform the codification is necessary to define a threshold TH in Equation 10. LZC ranges from 0 (deterministic sequence) to 1 (random sequence) [29].

$$s(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x(t) < \text{TH} \\ 1 & \text{if } x(t) \geq \text{TH} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

2.2 Poincaré Section

The Poincaré Section is the intersection of an orbit in the phase space of a continuous dynamical system with an hyperplane transverse to the flow of the trajectory of the phase space. The Poincaré section is used to reduce the dimensionality of the phase space, and to transform the continuous flow time into a discrete time map. The time variation of a trajectory between two successive intersection points depend both of the trajectories in the phase space, and on the surface chosen for the intersection. Each period leads at least to one point in the Poincaré Section. The map iterations are given by the point where the trajectory intersects the surface in a specific direction, as it is shown in Figure 2.

Although it does not exist any general method to build the Poincaré maps, it is implemented maximum return mapping. Return maps plots a pairs of points

Fig. 2 Poincaré Section of a surface

(x_t, x_{t+1}) with x_t as the t -th point in the Poincaré section, and maximum return mapping is where this map (x_t, x_{t+1}) maps two consecutive maximum values, being the new map represented by (max_t, max_{t+1}) .

Fig. 3 Poincaré Sections from gait signal produced by A: an HC subject, B: PD patient in low state of the disease (MDS-UPDRS-III=6 for lower limbs), C: PD patient in intermediate state of the disease (MDS-UPDRS-III=13 for lower limbs). D: PD patient in severe state of the disease (MDS-UPDRS-III=34 for lower limbs)

After the reconstruction of Poincaré Sections, a clustering algorithm is performed to model the maps in a probabilistic way. We consider a GMM to model the sections of the map with the aim to extract features from the Gaussian clusters. Figure 3 shows examples of the Poincaré maps and clusters extracted with the GMM. Note that there are differences in the maps obtained from the different subjects. The map obtained for the HC subject 3.A and for the patient in low state of the disease 3.B reflect more data concentration than the maps computed for the patients in intermediate (Figure 3.C) or severe state of the disease (Figure 3.D), which are more sparse.

2.2.1 Gaussian Mixture Model

The GMM is a clustering algorithm that implements the Expectation Maximization algorithm (EM) to find the mixed Gaussian probability distribution that best model a data distribution. To find the initial values the GMM algorithm is initialized By means of the K-Means algorithm. Then, it is assume that each sample is generated by a probability distribution. The goal is to estimate the parameters μ_k (means), Σ_k (co-variances) y ω (weight of the mixture) according to the maximum likelihood, computed according to Equation 11.

$$L(\mathbf{X}|\Theta) = \prod_{t=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^K \omega_k P_k(\mathbf{x}_t|\Theta_k) \quad (11)$$

Where K is the number of clusters in the Θ model, n is the number of observations (feature vectors), \mathbf{x}_t is the t -th feature vector and Θ_k is the set of Gaussian parameters μ_k and Σ_k . P_k is the probability density distribution, which is estimated using Equation 12, where d is the number of features. The means vector μ_k and the co-variances vector Σ_k determine the centers and geometric characteristics of each Gaussian component.

$$P_k(\mathbf{x}_t|\theta_k) = \frac{\exp(-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x}_t - \mu_k)^T \Sigma_k^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_t - \mu_k))}{\sqrt{(2\pi)^d \Sigma_k}} \quad (12)$$

Fig. 4 Representation of the characteristics of a gaussian

In Figure 4 is shown the characteristics that compounds a gaussian such as its mean μ and for the co-variance matrix Σ its eigenvalues λ and eigenvectors \mathbf{u} . Σ can be taken as symmetric, defined it according to this eigenvector an values in Equation 13.

$$\Sigma \mathbf{u}_i = \lambda_i \mathbf{u}_i \quad (13)$$

Then, expressing Σ in terms of its eigenvector, it takes the form defined in Equation 14, where D corresponds to the dimension.

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \sum_{i=1}^D i u_i u_i^T \quad (14)$$

According to the above, we based on the characteristics that compounds a gaussian to the Feature extraction such as $\boldsymbol{\mu}$, $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ and ω .

2.3 Classification and Regression Methods

2.3.1 *K-Nearest-Neighbors*

The main aim of the KNN classifier is to assign a new sample of the test data into one of the classes depending on the number of K neighbors of each class that are closer to the test sample. The decision is made based on the majority of the number of neighbors that belong to each class. The Euclidian distance is used to determine the K nearest neighbors of the test sample.

2.3.2 *Support Vector Machine*

The aim of a SVM is to discriminate data samples using a separating hyperplane that maximizes the margin between two classes. The decision function of the SVM is expressed according to Equation 15. For this case, the SVM is known as soft-margin SVM, which is known by allow some errors in the optimization process of finding the optimal hyperplane. The term ξ_n is a slack variable to penalize the amount of errors allowed in the optimization process. $y_n \in \{-1, +1\}$ are the class labels, $\phi(\mathbf{x}_n)$ is a kernel function to transform the feature space \mathbf{x} into a higher dimensional space where a linear solution of the problem may be found. The weight vector \mathbf{w} and the bias value b are the terms which define the separating hyperplane.

$$y_n \cdot (\mathbf{w}^T \phi(\mathbf{x}_n) + b) \geq 1 - \xi_n, \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N \quad (15)$$

The optimization problem to find the hyperplane is given by Equation 16, where the hyper-parameter C controls the trade-off between ξ_n and the width of the margin. The samples \mathbf{x}_n where the condition $y \cdot (\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x} + b) = 1 - \xi_n$ are called support vectors (\mathbf{x}_m).

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\mathbf{w}, b}{\text{minimize}} && \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{w}\|^2 + C \sum_{n=1}^N \xi_n \\ & \text{subject to} && y \cdot (\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x}_n + b) \geq 1 - \xi_n \\ & && \xi_n \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

We consider a Gaussian kernel function $\phi(\mathbf{x}_n)$, which is given by Equation 17, where the hyper-parameter γ is the bandwidth of the kernel function.

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}_n) = e^{-\gamma^2 \|\mathbf{x}_n - \mathbf{x}_m\|^2} \quad (17)$$

2.4 Random Forest

The RF is one of the most used ensemble methods, which are based on the combination of multiple algorithms to make the final decision. Particularly, the RF combines several simpler classifiers such as the decision trees. Each decision tree makes a local decision about the class using different set of the features. Each decision tree performed a local classification with a subset of the original feature space. Finally, a voting scheme is performed between the decisions performed by each tree. The hyper-parameters to optimize the RF are the number of trees used to make the local decisions (N), and the maximum depth of the trees (D).

2.4.1 *Support Vector Regression*

The prediction of the neurological state of patients according to the MDS-UPDRS-III scale is performed using a SVR with lineal kernel. This technique allows to predict the value of the scale (\hat{y}) using a loss function $L(y, \hat{y})$ that ensures the existence of global optimum. This function is calculated by Equation 18, where ε is an insensitive hyper-parameter to determine the maximum error allowed in the prediction..

$$L(y, \hat{y}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } |y - \hat{y}| \leq \varepsilon \\ |y - \hat{y}| - \varepsilon & \text{in other cases.} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

The feature vectors \mathbf{x} are mapped into a m -dimensional space using a kernel $\phi(\mathbf{x})$ function. The predicted values \hat{y} are estimated in the same way as in the SVM classifier, according to Equation 15, where \mathbf{w} establishes the weight of each support vector, and b is the independent term.

3 Database

Gait signals were captured with the eGait system¹, which consists of a 3D-accelerometer (range $\pm 6g$) and a 3D gyroscope (range $\pm 500^\circ/s$) attached to the lateral heel of the shoes [9]. Figure 5 shows the eGait system and the inertial sensor attached to the lateral heel of the shoe. The signals are transmitted by bluetooth to a tablet where they are received by an android app.

¹ Embedded Gait analysis using Intelligent Technology, <http://www.egait.de/>

Data from both foot were captured with a sampling frequency of 100Hz and 12-bit resolution. The tasks performed by the patients include 20 meters walking with a stop at 10 meters (Two times 10 m walk, 2x10m), and 40 meters walking with a stop every 10 meters (Four times 10 m walk, 4x10m).

Fig. 5 Interface eGaiT and shoe with its attached inertial sensor.

Data are obtained from 45 PD patients and 45 HC subjects. The patients were evaluated by an expert neurologist and labeled according to the MDS-UPDRS-III score. Table 1 shows additional information of the participants of this study.

Table 1 General information of the subjects. **PD** patients: Parkinson’s disease patients. **HC**: healthy controls. μ : average. σ : standard deviation. **T**: disease duration.

	PD patients		HC subjects	
	male	female	male	female
Number of subjects	17	28	23	22
Age ($\mu \pm \sigma$)	65 \pm 10.3	58.9 \pm 11.0	66.3 \pm 11.5	59.0 \pm 9.8
Range of age	41-82	29-75	49-84	50-74
T ($\mu \pm \sigma$)	9 \pm 4.6	12.6 \pm 12.2		
Range of duration of the disease	2-15	0-44		
MDS-UPDRS-III ($\mu \pm \sigma$)	37.6 \pm 21.0	33 \pm 20.3		
Range of MDS-UPDRS-III	8-82	9-106		
Range of MDS-UPDRS-III (Lower Limbs)	3-41	0-50		

4 Experiments and results

Three experiments were performed: (1) Classification of PD patients and HC subjects, (2) Prediction of the neurological state of the patients according to the MDS-UPDRS-III sub-score for lower limbs, and (3) The classification of PD patients in several stages of the disease. Three set of features were considered in each experiment: (1) The NLD and entropy features, described in Section 2.1, (2) the features extracted from Poincaré sections using the GMM approach, described in Section 2.2, and (3) the combination of both feature sets.

For all experiments, we follow a 5-fold cross-validation strategy, where 3 folds were used for training, one to optimize the hyper-parameters of the classifiers, i.e., development set, and one for test respectively. The parameters were optimized in a grid search over the train folds. For the case of KNN, we optimize the number of neighbors $K \in \{3, 5, \dots, 11\}$. For the SVM, we optimize the complexity parameter $C \in \{10^{-4}, 10^{-3}, \dots, 10^4\}$ and the bandwidth of the kernel $\gamma \in \{10^{-4}, 10^{-3}, \dots, 10^4\}$. For the RF, we optimize the number of trees $N \in \{5, 10, 20, 30, 50, 100\}$ and the maximum depth of the trees $D \in \{2, 5, 10, 20, 30, 50, 100\}$. A similar approach is performed with the SVR for the regression experiment. In this case we optimize the complexity parameter $C \in \{10^{-6}, 10^{-5}, \dots, 10^4\}$ and the insensitive parameter $\varepsilon \in \{0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 1, 10, 50, 100\}$. The performance of the regression method is obtained with the Spearman’s correlation coefficient ρ .

4.1 Classification of PD patients and HC subjects

Three experiments were performed for this classification task depending on the feature set, considering: (1) only NLD and entropy features, (2) the features extracted from Poincaré sections and GMMs, and (3) the combination of both feature sets. The results obtained for these feature sets are shown in Tables 2, 3 and 4, respectively. In addition, individual experiments are performed by foot and per gait exercises, and the features computed from the two tasks and feet are combined based on an early fusion strategy.

Table 2 shows relatively high accuracies, especially when we combined the features from both tasks and both feet (85.6% obtained with the RF classifier). The separate classification using features computed from each foot show that the highest accuracies were obtained for the left foot, which may indicate that the left part of the lower limbs are more affected due to the disease. This fact can be explained due to the cross laterality effect [30], taking into account that most of the patients are right dominant foot. The results also show that the

Table 2 Results of NLD Features to classify PD patients vs. HC subjects considering NLD and entropy features. **ACC**: accuracy in the test set, **AUC**: Area under ROC curve. μ : average. σ : standard deviation.

Foot	Task	KNN			SVM			RF		
		ACC(%) ($\mu \pm \sigma$)	Sen(%) / Spe(%)	AUC	ACC(%) ($\mu \pm \sigma$)	Sen(%) / Spe(%)	AUC	ACC(%) ($\mu \pm \sigma$)	Sen(%) / Spe(%)	AUC
Left	2x10	81.1 \pm 9.3	80.0/82.2	0.84	77.8 \pm 13.0	66.7/88.9	0.74	83.3 \pm 14.2	73.3/93.3	0.89
Left	4x10	72.2 \pm 11.1	68.9/75.6	0.80	81.1 \pm 12.8	86.7/75.6	0.90	84.4 \pm 7.2	82.2/86.7	0.89
Left	Fusion	80.0 \pm 8.4	73.3/86.7	0.86	83.3 \pm 6.8	82.2/84.4	0.84	83.3 \pm 8.8	77.8/88.9	0.89
Right	2x10	70.0 \pm 9.3	60.0/80.0	0.82	67.8 \pm 7.2	51.1/84.4	0.73	78.9 \pm 6.1	73.3/84.4	0.79
Right	4x10	77.8 \pm 6.8	73.3/82.2	0.82	76.7 \pm 7.2	73.3/80.0	0.83	80.0 \pm 11.5	80.0/80.0	0.87
Right	Fusion	81.1 \pm 8.4	73.3/88.9	0.85	82.2 \pm 4.6	75.6/88.9	0.87	85.6 \pm 6.3	82.2/88.9	0.91
Both	2x10	76.7 \pm 12.7	68.9/84.4	0.79	80.0 \pm 8.4	68.9/91.1	0.85	78.9 \pm 11.4	71.1/86.7	0.86
Both	4x10	72.2 \pm 3.9	75.6/68.9	0.80	81.1 \pm 6.3	77.8/84.4	0.83	82.2 \pm 12.7	82.2/82.2	0.91
Both	Fusion	85.6 \pm 5.0	77.8/93.3	0.89	82.2 \pm 4.6	71.1/93.3	0.86	85.6 \pm 2.5	80.0/91.1	0.91

specificity (91.1% for the RF classifier when the features are combined) is higher than sensitivity (80.0% in the same scenario), which indicates that our system is more accurate to detect correctly the HC subjects.

In comparison to the results from the set of NLD Features from Table 2, a higher accuracy was obtained with the Poincaré features in Table 3. The Poincaré features keep the premise that the fusion of both feet and tasks are more effective to discriminate between PD patients and HC subjects. Although the accuracy obtained with the Poincaré features seems to be reduced respect to the reported with the NLD and entropy features (especially for the KNN and SVM classifiers), note that the highest accuracy improved in up to 1.1% the highest one obtained with the NLD and entropy features.

Results for the combination of NLD, entropy, and Poincaré features (see Table 4) show that the highest accuracy is obtained with the SVM classifier (86.7%). This result is the same as the obtained only with the Poincaré features; however, the feature combination provides more stable results in terms of the specificity and sensitivity. Note also the presence of the cross-laterality effect in the results, i.e., the highest accuracies are obtained with the features computed from the left foot.

4.2 Regression: Neurological State Prediction

Table 5 shows the results of the prediction of the neurological state of the patients according to the MDS-UPDRS-III subscore for lower limbs. In general, the highest correlations are obtained for the NLD features (ρ up to 0.31).

4.2.1 Classification of patients in several stages of the disease

Although there is some correlation between the predicted and the real MDS-UPDRS-III scores, we believe that from the clinical point of view it is more suitable

for the patients to know in which stage of the disease they are, rather than to have the prediction of a continuous scale. In addition, for medical applications is difficult to have a great amount of data to train suitable regression algorithms like an SVR. For those reasons we believe that it is better to divide the patients into three groups according to their neurological state: lower, intermediate, and severe. Figure 6 shows the division of the neurological stage of the patients into the three groups. Additionally, HC subjects are considered as a separate group to perform a four-class classification strategy.

Fig. 6 Histogram for the neurological state of the patients according to the MDS-UPDRS-III subscore for lower limbs. Patients in initial stage (green), patients in intermediate stage (yellow), and patients in severe stage (purple).

Table 6 shows the results of performing a Multi-Class Classification for the NLD Features. The highest accuracies are also obtained with the signals captured with the combination of features from both sensors and with the RF classifier (63.3%), as in the previous experiments when we discriminate only PD patients and HC subjects. The κ -index (0.41) indicates moderate agreement in the classification.

Table 3 Results of Poincaré Features to classify PD patients vs. HC subjects. **ACC**: accuracy in the test set, **AUC**: Area under ROC curve. μ : average. σ : standard deviation.

Foot	Task	KNN			SVM			RF		
		ACC(%) ($\mu \pm \sigma$)	Sen(%) / Spe(%)	AUC	ACC(%) ($\mu \pm \sigma$)	Sen(%) / Spe(%)	AUC	ACC(%) ($\mu \pm \sigma$)	Sen(%) / Spe(%)	AUC
Left	2x10	67.8 \pm 4.1	53.3/82.2	0.70	68.9 \pm 8.3	64.4/73.3	0.74	77.8 \pm 6.1	77.8/77.8	0.85
Left	4x10	62.2 \pm 10.7	46.7/77.8	0.65	72.2 \pm 3.5	73.3/71.1	0.81	72.2 \pm 10.5	71.1/73.3	0.77
Left	Fusion	57.8 \pm 9.0	37.8/77.8	0.66	57.8 \pm 4.4	53.3/62.2	0.63	86.7 \pm 2.7	80.0/93.3	0.91
Right	2x10	61.1 \pm 11.6	44.4/77.8	0.68	81.1 \pm 7.5	77.8/84.4	0.86	85.6 \pm 5.6	77.8/93.3	0.87
Right	4x10	54.4 \pm 9.5	42.2/66.7	0.61	72.2 \pm 9.9	71.1/73.3	0.80	71.1 \pm 8.1	68.9/73.3	0.79
Right	Fusion	57.8 \pm 9.0	35.6/80.0	0.66	72.2 \pm 14.4	71.1/73.3	0.80	82.2 \pm 8.8	82.2/82.2	0.86
Both	2x10	61.1 \pm 6.1	37.8/84.4	0.70	77.8 \pm 7.0	77.8/77.8	0.87	82.2 \pm 2.2	82.2/82.2	0.90
Both	4x10	63.3 \pm 7.5	46.7/80.0	0.71	73.3 \pm 6.4	73.3/73.3	0.80	76.7 \pm 6.5	75.6/77.8	0.84
Both	Fusion	65.6 \pm 8.2	35.6/95.6	0.71	81.1 \pm 5.7	75.6/86.7	0.87	86.7 \pm 2.7	80.0/93.3	0.91

Table 4 Results of NLD+Poincaré features to classify PD patients vs. HC subjects. **ACC**: accuracy in the test set, **AUC**: Area under ROC curve. μ : average. σ : standard deviation.

Foot	Task	KNN			SVM			RF		
		ACC(%) ($\mu \pm \sigma$)	Sen(%) / Spe(%)	AUC	ACC(%) ($\mu \pm \sigma$)	Sen(%) / Spe(%)	AUC	ACC(%) ($\mu \pm \sigma$)	Sen(%) / Spe(%)	AUC
Left	2x10	77.8 \pm 11.6	66.7/88.9	0.85	80.0 \pm 6.7	73.3/86.7	0.82	82.2 \pm 9.5	80.0/84.4	0.88
Left	4x10	78.9 \pm 7.3	66.7/91.1	0.86	82.2 \pm 4.1	82.2/82.2	0.89	84.4 \pm 8.1	77.8/91.1	0.90
Left	Fusion	83.3 \pm 6.0	73.3/93.3	0.91	86.7 \pm 8.3	88.9/84.4	0.91	85.6 \pm 9.0	73.3/97.8	0.93
Right	2x10	67.8 \pm 4.1	40.0/95.6	0.75	80.0 \pm 7.5	68.9/91.1	0.86	77.8 \pm 3.5	68.9/86.7	0.85
Right	4x10	78.9 \pm 4.1	73.3/84.4	0.84	78.9 \pm 9.5	77.8/80.0	0.76	77.8 \pm 15.3	84.4/71.1	0.81
Right	Fusion	75.6 \pm 7.5	60.0/91.1	0.82	76.7 \pm 7.4	71.1/82.2	0.81	82.2 \pm 4.1	80.0/84.4	0.88
Both	2x10	74.4 \pm 7.5	53.3/95.6	0.84	78.9 \pm 4.1	71.1/86.7	0.83	85.6 \pm 4.4	80.0/91.1	0.92
Both	4x10	76.7 \pm 7.3	64.4/88.9	0.87	81.1 \pm 7.5	84.4/77.8	0.82	80.0 \pm 5.7	75.6/84.4	0.88
Both	Fusion	77.8 \pm 6.1	57.8/97.8	0.89	83.3 \pm 7.9	82.2/84.4	0.91	84.4 \pm 5.4	82.2/86.7	0.90

Table 5 Results of the Neurological State Prediction. **MAE**: mean absolute error. ρ : Spearman's Correlation.

Foot	Task	NLD Features		Poincaré Features		NLD+ Poincaré Features	
		ρ	MAE	ρ	MAE	ρ	MAE
Left	2x10	-0.13	10.19	-0.31	9.10	-0.20	8.02
Left	4x10	0.16	6.93	-0.15	11.74	0.08	7.70
Left	Fusion	0.07	8.88	-0.09	8.44	-0.15	8.37
Right	2x10	0.19	8.43	0.16	10.82	-0.02	9.44
Right	4x10	-0.00	10.77	-0.24	14.37	0.17	9.64
Right	Fusion	0.31	8.00	-0.02	11.41	-0.05	8.71
Both	2x10	0.26	8.25	0.18	8.45	0.16	8.98
Both	4x10	0.30	7.57	0.09	9.41	0.03	8.30
Both	Fusion	0.31	8.26	-0.09	8.46	0.07	7.93

Table 6 Results of Multi-Class Classification for NLD Measurements. **ACC**: accuracy in the test set. κ : Cohen's kappa index.

Foot	Task	KNN		SVM		RF	
		ACC (%)	κ	ACC (%)	κ	ACC (%)	κ
Left	2x10	54.4 \pm 6.5	0.22	61.1 \pm 9.9	0.36	61.1 \pm 7.0	0.37
Left	4x10	56.7 \pm 4.2	0.25	58.9 \pm 9.6	0.32	60.0 \pm 4.2	0.33
Left	Fusion	62.2 \pm 9.5	0.37	62.2 \pm 13.3	0.40	61.1 \pm 12.1	0.34
Right	2x10	52.2 \pm 4.4	0.17	57.8 \pm 5.6	0.29	57.8 \pm 10.3	0.30
Right	4x10	52.2 \pm 9.0	0.19	58.9 \pm 5.6	0.34	50.0 \pm 11.3	0.15
Right	Fusion	55.6 \pm 4.9	0.25	54.4 \pm 8.8	0.27	56.7 \pm 8.8	0.25
Both	2x10	56.7 \pm 9.6	0.28	55.6 \pm 6.0	0.24	63.3 \pm 6.7	0.41
Both	4x10	50.0 \pm 6.0	0.18	56.7 \pm 9.5	0.30	55.6 \pm 9.2	0.23
Both	Fusion	60.0 \pm 8.1	0.36	51.1 \pm 5.4	0.18	62.2 \pm 7.3	0.40

The results when the Poincaré features are considered are shown in Table 7. In general, the accuracy is reduced in around 3.4% respect to the obtained with the classical NLD and entropy features. However, note that the standard deviation is lower when we consider the Poincaré features, which make the results more stable across different partitions of the test set.

Table 7 Results of Multi-Class Classification for Poincaré Measurements. **ACC**: accuracy in the test set. κ : Cohen's kappa index.

Foot	Task	KNN		SVM		RF	
		ACC (%)	κ	ACC (%)	κ	ACC (%)	κ
Left	2x10	51.1 \pm 8.2	0.14	51.1 \pm 4.2	0.18	50.0 \pm 3.5	0.10
Left	4x10	54.4 \pm 9.5	0.18	56.7 \pm 13.3	0.29	50.0 \pm 3.5	0.10
Left	Fusion	52.2 \pm 2.7	0.13	56.7 \pm 9.5	0.29	52.2 \pm 6.6	0.17
Right	2x10	52.2 \pm 2.7	0.14	55.6 \pm 5.0	0.22	57.8 \pm 9.6	0.25
Right	4x10	42.2 \pm 4.4	-0.10	51.1 \pm 2.2	0.10	53.3 \pm 5.6	0.16
Right	Fusion	50.0 \pm 3.5	0.10	51.1 \pm 2.2	0.11	53.3 \pm 8.3	0.21
Both	2x10	47.8 \pm 5.6	0.04	48.9 \pm 2.2	0.10	54.4 \pm 4.2	0.22
Both	4x10	46.7 \pm 4.4	-0.01	51.1 \pm 8.8	0.20	50.0 \pm 3.5	0.12
Both	Fusion	48.9 \pm 2.2	0.05	51.1 \pm 7.3	0.18	53.3 \pm 5.7	0.15

The results when we combine the classical NLD and the Poincaré features are shown in Table 8. This early-fusion strategy shows to be the most accurate to discriminate between PD patients in several stages of the disease and HC subjects. We obtain accuracies up to 65.2%, which is slightly higher than the obtained only with the NLD features. This fact indicates that our proposed features based on Poincaré sections and GMM models provide complementary information to the classical NLD analysis about the non-linear effects of the gait process of PD patients.

Table 9 shows the confusion matrices for the best results of the multi-class experiment when we consider only the NLD features, only the Poincaré based measures, and the combination of both feature sets. The confusion matrices for the three feature sets indicate that HC subjects are accurately classified compared to patients in different stages, i.e., the proposed approach

Table 8 Results of Multi-Class Classification for NLD+Poincaré Measurements. **ACC**: accuracy in the test set. κ : Cohen’s kappa index.

Foot	Task	KNN		SVM		RF	
		ACC (%)	κ	ACC (%)	κ	ACC (%)	κ
Left	2x10	49.5±6.6	0.08	58.5±5.1	0.32	57.1±9.3	0.26
Left	4x10	50.1±3.7	0.12	60.1±6.1	0.34	58.4±7.8	0.26
Left	Fusion	57.3±4.1	0.21	65.2±8.1	0.43	61.8±5.2	0.33
Right	2x10	53.9±4.1	0.11	55.1±5.7	0.25	52.8±2.5	0.14
Right	4x10	53.9±7.0	0.16	60.7±7.1	0.34	58.9±4.9	0.24
Right	Fusion	56.1±4.4	0.18	54.0±9.2	0.20	60.6±5.6	0.31
Both	2x10	52.9±5.0	0.11	60.7±9.0	0.29	61.8±5.6	0.34
Both	4x10	56.2±6.2	0.20	61.8±6.2	0.37	51.6±3.3	0.14
Both	Fusion	59.6±6.1	0.25	64.1±8.0	0.38	59.5±4.1	0.28

has a high specificity. The group of PD patients in severe stage of the disease (PD.3) seems to be the most difficult group to classify correctly, which could be explained due to the high variability of the original MDS-UPDRS-III score for those patients (see Figure 6).

5 Discussion and Conclusions

Gait signals captured from inertial sensors of PD patients were characterized with several NLD-based features to model non-linear effects in the walking process of the patients. The extracted features are related to stability, chaotic dynamics, long-term dependency, and complexity, and include classical NLD features such as CD, LLE, HE, and several entropy measures. In addition, we proposed a new characterization scheme based on a clustering analysis of Poincaré sections using a GMM algorithm. The extracted features were used to classify PD patients and HC subjects, to predict the neurological state of the patients, and to classify patients in several stages of the disease.

The results show that it is possible to discriminate between PD patients and HC subjects with accuracies up to 85.6%, using the proposed NLD analysis. The proposed NLD features based on Poincaré sections also provide complementary information to the classical NLD features to discriminate between PD patients and HC subjects. The results also indicate the presence of the cross laterality effect [30], since higher accuracies are obtained classifying the features computed from the left foot rather than those computed from the right foot, although most of the subjects from this study are right-dominant foot.

The proposed approach seems to be promising to classify PD patients in different stages of the disease. The combination of the classical NLD features with the proposed features from Poincaré sections is also the most accurate approach to classify PD patients in several stages of the disease (up to 65.2%). Patients in lower stages of disease are mainly miss-classified with HC subjects, which is explained due to in the early

stages of the disease, the symptoms appear mainly only in the upper limbs. PD patients in severe stages of the disease are miss-classified mainly due to the those patients are more spread out in terms of the original MDS-UPDRS scale than the other groups of patients. Additional labeled data is need to improve the accuracy to classify patients in several stages of the disease.

The proposed approach can be extended to other applications. For instance the discrimination between PD and other neurological disorders with similar symptoms, such as Huntington’s disease, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, or essential tremor. There is evidence for this application in the literature [17,31]. The proposed features can also be considered to analyze movement signals. Besides, following the same line of NLD, it can be considered other features such as Recurrency Quantification Analysis (RQA), that has been applied in gait analysis in different injuries and diseases as in related work [17,32].

Figure 7 shows MDS-UPDRS score sheet used for the neurologist in this study [2]. Highlighter is found the part 3 of this scale related to the motor symptoms, where it was selected only the items related with the lower limbs (see Figure 10).

Acknowledgements This work was financed by CODI from University of Antioquia grant #2015-7683. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Grant Agreement No. 766287.

References

1. O. Hornykiewicz. Biochemical aspects of Parkinson’s disease. *Neurology*, 51(2 Suppl 2):S2–S9, 1998.
2. C. G. Goetz, et al. Movement Disorder Society-sponsored revision of the Unified Parkinson’s Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS): Scale presentation and clinimetric testing results. *Movement Disorders*, 23(15):2129–2170, 2008.
3. V. E. Kelly, A. J. Eusterbrock, and A. Shumway-Cook. A review of dual-task walking deficits in people with parkinson’s disease: motor and cognitive contributions, mechanisms, and clinical implications. *Parkinson’s Disease*, 2012:1–14, 2012.
4. P. M. Coen, S. A. Jubrias, G. Distefano, et al. Skeletal muscle mitochondrial energetics are associated with maximal aerobic capacity and walking speed in older adults. *Journals of Gerontology Series A: Biomedical Sciences and Medical Sciences*, 68(4):447–455, 2012.
5. C. J. Hass et al. Quantitative normative gait data in a large cohort of ambulatory persons with parkinson’s disease. *PloS one*, 7(8):e42337, 2012.
6. Q. W. Oung, H. Muthusamy, et al. Technologies for assessment of motor disorders in Parkinson’s disease: a review. *Sensors*, 15(9):21710–21745, 2015.
7. J. Barth, J. Klucken, et al. Biometric and mobile gait analysis for early diagnosis and therapy monitoring in

_____	_____	____ - ____ - ____ (mm-dd-yyyy) Assessment Date	_____
Patient Name or Subject ID	Site ID		Investigator's Initials

MDS UPDRS Score Sheet

1.A	Source of information	<input type="checkbox"/> Patient	3.3b	Rigidity- RUE	
		<input type="checkbox"/> Caregiver	3.3c	Rigidity- LUE	
			3.3d	Rigidity- RLE	
Part I			3.3e	Rigidity- LLE	
1.1	Cognitive impairment		3.4a	Finger tapping- Right hand	
1.2	Hallucinations and psychosis		3.4b	Finger tapping- Left hand	
1.3	Depressed mood		3.5a	Hand movements- Right hand	
1.4	Anxious mood		3.5b	Hand movements- Left hand	
1.5	Apathy		3.6a	Pronation- supination movements- Right hand	
1.6	Features of DDS		3.6b	Pronation- supination movements- Left hand	
1.6a	Who is filling out questionnaire	<input type="checkbox"/> Patient	3.7a	Toe tapping- Right foot	
		<input type="checkbox"/> Caregiver			
		<input type="checkbox"/> Patient + Caregiver	3.7b	Toe tapping- Left foot	
1.7	Sleep problems		3.8a	Leg agility- Right leg	
1.8	Daytime sleepiness		3.8b	Leg agility- Left leg	
1.9	Pain and other sensations		3.9	Arising from chair	
1.10	Urinary problems		3.10	Gait	
1.11	Constipation problems		3.11	Freezing of gait	
1.12	Light headedness on standing		3.12	Postural stability	
1.13	Fatigue		3.13	Posture	
Part II			3.14	Global spontaneity of movement	
2.1	Speech		3.15a	Postural tremor- Right hand	
2.2	Saliva and drooling		3.15b	Postural tremor- Left hand	
2.3	Chewing and swallowing		3.16a	Kinetic tremor- Right hand	
2.4	Eating tasks		3.16b	Kinetic tremor- Left hand	
2.5	Dressing		3.17a	Rest tremor amplitude- RUE	
2.6	Hygiene		3.17b	Rest tremor amplitude- LUE	
2.7	Handwriting		3.17c	Rest tremor amplitude- RLE	
2.8	Doing hobbies and other activities		3.17d	Rest tremor amplitude- LLE	
2.9	Turning in bed		3.17e	Rest tremor amplitude- Lip/jaw	
2.10	Tremor		3.18	Constancy of rest	
2.11	Getting out of bed			Were dyskinesias present?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes
2.12	Walking and balance			Did these movements interfere with ratings?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes
2.13	Freezing			Hoehn and Yahr Stage	
3a	Is the patient on medication?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	Part IV		
3b	Patient's clinical state	<input type="checkbox"/> Off <input type="checkbox"/> On	4.1	Time spent with dyskinesias	
3c	Is the patient on Levodopa?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	4.2	Functional impact of dyskinesias	
3.C1	If yes, minutes since last dose:		4.3	Time spent in the OFF state	
Part III			4.4	Functional impact of fluctuations	
3.1	Speech		4.5	Complexity of motor fluctuations	
3.2	Facial expression		4.6	Painful OFF-state dystonia	
3.3a	Rigidity- Neck				

Copyright © 2008 International Parkinson and Movement Disorder Society. All rights reserved

This scale may not be copied, distributed or otherwise used in whole or in part without prior written consent of the International Parkinson and Movement Disorder Society

Fig. 7 Movement Disorder Society–Unified Parkinson Disease Rating Scale

Table 9 Confusion Matrices of Multi-Class Classification for best results in each experiment. **HC:** HC subjects. **PD_1:** MDS-UPDRS III (Lower Limbs) ranging between 0-10. **PD_2:** MDS-UPDRS III (Lower Limbs) ranging between 11-17. **PD_3:** MDS-UPDRS III (Lower Limbs) of 18+.

Class	NLD Features Both 2x10m RF				Poincaré Features Right 2x10m RF				NLD+Poincaré Features Left Fusion SVM			
	HC	PD_1	PD_2	PD_3	HC	PD_1	PD_2	PD_3	HC	PD_1	PD_2	PD_3
HC	45	0	0	0	43	0	2	0	41	1	3	0
PD_1	3	2	5	5	8	4	2	1	5	4	3	2
PD_2	7	1	5	2	9	1	4	1	5	0	11	0
PD_3	3	2	5	5	8	4	2	1	6	4	3	2

Table 10 Lower limbs items of MDS-UPDRS-III

Part III	
3.3d	Ridigity-RLE
3.3e	Ridigity-LLE
3.7a	Toe tapping-Right foot
3.7b	Toe tapping-Left foot
3.8a	Leg agility-Right leg
3.8b	Leg agility-Left leg
3.9	Arising from chair
3.10	Gait
3.11	Freezing of gait
3.12	Postural stability
3.13	Posture
3.14	Global spontaneity of movement
3.17c	Rest tremor amplitude-RLE
3.17d	Rest tremor amplitude-LLE

parkinson's disease. In *2011 Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society*, pages 868–871, 2011.

8. F. Parisi, G. Ferrari, et al. Body-sensor-network-based kinematic characterization and comparative outlook of UPDRS scoring in leg agility, sit-to-stand, and gait tasks in Parkinson's disease. *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, 19(6):1777–1793, 2015.
9. J. Klucken, J. Barth, et al. Unbiased and mobile gait analysis detects motor impairment in Parkinson's disease. *PloS one*, 8(2):e56956, 2013.
10. eGaIT - embedded Gait analysis using Intelligent Technology, <http://www.egait.de/>, 2018.
11. Ö .F. Ertugrul, Y. Kaya, R. Tekin, et al. Detection of parkinson's disease by shifted one dimensional local binary patterns from gait. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 56:156–163, 2016.
12. P. Ren, W. Zhao, Z. Zhao, et al. Analysis of gait rhythm fluctuations for neurodegenerative diseases by phase synchronization and conditional entropy. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, 24(2):291–299, 2016.
13. J. C. Vasquez-Correa et al. Multi-view representation learning via gcca for multimodal analysis of parkinson's disease. In *International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, pages 2966–2970, 2017.
14. J. Hannink, H. Gaßner, et al. Inertial sensor-based estimation of peak accelerations during heel-strike and loading as markers of impaired gait patterns in PD patients. *Basal Ganglia*, 8:1, 2017.
15. J. Camps, A. Sama, M. Martin, et al. Deep learning for freezing of gait detection in parkinson's disease patients in their homes using a waist-worn inertial measurement unit. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 139:119–131, 2018.
16. E. Sejdic et al. A comprehensive assessment of gait accelerometry signals in time, frequency and time-frequency domains. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, 22(3):603–612, 2014.
17. P. Prabhu, A. Karunakar, H. Anitha, et al. Classification of gait signals into different neurodegenerative diseases using statistical analysis and recurrence quantification analysis. *Pattern Recognition Letters (IN PRESS)*, 2018.
18. Physionet-Gait Dynamics in Neuro-Degenerative Disease Data Base, <https://physionet.org/physiobank/database/gaitnnd/>, 2018.
19. J. R. Orozco-Arroyave et al. Analysis of speech from people with parkinson's disease through nonlinear dynamics. In *International Conference on Nonlinear Speech Processing*, pages 112–119. Springer, 2013.
20. R. K. Begg, M. Palaniswami, and B. Owen. Support vector machines for automated gait classification. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 52(5):828–838, 2005.
21. F. Takens. On the numerical determination of the dimension of an attractor. *Lecture notes in mathematics*, 1125(11):99–106, 1985.
22. H. Kantz and T. Schreiber. *Nonlinear time series analysis*, volume 7. Cambridge university press, 2004.
23. M. B. Kennel et al. Determining embedding dimension for phase-space reconstruction using a geometrical construction. *Physical review A*, 45(6):3403, 1992.
24. J. S. Richman and J. R. Moorman. Physiological time-series analysis using approximate entropy and sample entropy. *American Journal of Physiology-Heart and Circulatory Physiology*, 278(6):H2039–H2049, 2000.
25. L. Xu et al. Gaussian kernel approximate entropy algorithm for analyzing irregularity of time-series. In *International Conference on Machine Learning and Cybernetics*, pages 5605–5608, 2005.
26. V. I. Oseledets. A multiplicative ergodic theorem. characteristic l'japunov, exponents of dynamical systems. *Trudy Moskovskogo Matematicheskogo Obshchestva*, 19:179–210, 1968.
27. G. M. Mindlin and R. Gilmore. Topological analysis and synthesis of chaotic time series. *Physica D: Nonlinear Phenomena*, 58(1-4):229–242, 1992.
28. N. Radhakrishnan and B. N. Gangadhar. Estimating regularity in epileptic seizure time-series data. *IEEE engineering in medicine and biology magazine*, 17(3):89–94, 1998.
29. A. Lempel and J. Ziv. On the complexity of finite sequences. *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, 22(1):75–81, 1976.
30. H. Sadeghi, P. Allard, F. Prince, et al. Symmetry and limb dominance in able-bodied gait: a review. *Gait & posture*, 12(1):34–45, 2000.

-
31. G. Ebersbach et al. Clinical syndromes: Parkinsonian gait. *Movement Disorders*, 28(11):1552–1559, 2013.
 32. Hossein Negahban, Mahyar Salavati, Masood Mazaheri, Mohammad Ali Sanjari, Mohammad Reza Hadian, and Mohamad Parnianpour. Non-linear dynamical features of center of pressure extracted by recurrence quantification analysis in people with unilateral anterior cruciate ligament injury. *Gait & posture*, 31(4):450–455, 2010.